

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INVESTMENTS
IN LIVESTOCK FARMING

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик фаолиятининг қорамолчилик тармоғига сарфланаётган инвестициялар самарадорлигини оширишда таъсир қилувчи баъзи омиллар кўриб чиқилган. Қорамолчилик тармоғининг бугунги ҳолати таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар. Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик, инвестиция, маҳсулдорлик, ветеринария.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются некоторые факторы, влияющие на эффективность деятельности малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства на эффективность инвестиций в животноводческую сеть. Проанализировано современное состояние сети животноводства.

Ключевые слова. Малый бизнес и частное предпринимательство, инвестиции, производительность, Ветеринария.

Abstract. In this article examines some factors that influence the effectiveness of small business and private entrepreneurship activities on the efficiency of investment in the Cattle Breeding Network. The current state of the cattle network has been analyzed.

Keywords. Small business and private entrepreneurship, investment, productivity, veterinary.

Introduction. Development of small business and private entrepreneurship study

of the economic impact of attracting expended investments and study of theoretical and practical aspects of increasing efficiency has an important scientific and practical significance. It is known that the development of small business and private entrepreneurship as the essence of increasing the efficiency of investment spent consists in the production, services, profit and national income of greater volume of material, labor and financial expenditure evasion in each unit.

The study of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is one of the main pillars of the state, supporting the population in social and economic terms, affects the efficiency of the livestock sector on the development of factor and their characteristics is one of the pressing issues of today.

Literature review. The effective functioning of the investment sector of the economy is justifiably constantly in the focus of attention of scientists. Of particular theoretical and methodological significance is the analysis of problems and patterns of accumulation in the process of reproduction, which is given in the fundamental research of the classics of economic theory, J. Galbraith, K. Marx, J. Keynes, P. Samuelson. The system of state regulators and strategic planning is scientifically disclosed in the works of A. Wagner, V. Sombart, V. Kahn, V. Leontiev, F. Modigliani, S. Fischer, and D. Hyman. Problems of economic dynamics, optimal measurement of costs and results of labor, the ratio of fundaments products and capital productivity, macroeconomic forecasting, scientific and technological development and of the methodology of investments, update of the production apparatus, the intensification of the investment process and innovative production sector occupy an important place in the works of N. D. Kondratiev, A. I. Anchishkin, V. V. Novozhilov, A. I. Notkin, V. G. Lebedev, A. V. Bachurin, V. I. Kushlina, V. P. Loginov, J. A. Rekitar, Y. V. Yakovets.[6]

Research methodology: In the scientific paper, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, economic analysis, grouping, expert evaluation and comparison methods were used.

Analysis and Results. The government of the Republic develops many programs aimed at the development of livestock in all spheres of the country and implements a

number of measures to implement them into practice. In particular, the PP - 4576- decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures to support the state livestock network" adopted in Yanvar in 2020 was an important factor in the development of livestock. [1] The decision envisages the implementation of systematic measures and strategies aimed at increasing the efficiency of investments made by the state in the livestock sector, as well as being a program for today:

- development of measures to support the livestock and breeding sector by the state, to increase productivity and to develop the seed production of feeding crops;
- to organize an analysis of the effective use of land allocated to livestock farms and control the allocation of arable land in proportion to the number of cattle heads;
- to organize the activities of all branches of livestock on a scientific basis, to introduce the results of research and innovative works into the practice of product production and breeding-selection;
- addressing issues related to the development of the livestock processing sector, including the launch of new capacities and the expansion of the range of products;
- Organization of systematic training of personnel, improvement of their skills and retraining.

In the agricultural network, three main factors of production are the use of Natural Resources (Land and Water Resources), Capital (basic funds) and labor (employees of agricultural enterprises). These factors are the most important among these, without words-the Earth. At present, more than 20 million hectares of agricultural land, including 3.2 million hectares of irrigated land use in the Republic, food products for the needs of the population, the necessary raw materials for economic sectors are grown.

In particular, the agricultural areas of Andijan region comprise 26.1 thousand hectares of land, of which 23.4 thousand hectares are irrigated, the non-irrigated areas 3.1 thousand hectares, and the feed for livestock 3 thousand hectares. One of the

peculiarities of the region is that its population is the most densely populated in the Republic (up to 01.01.2020) the total population is 3127.7 thousand people, of which

47.7 percent live in villages. 1 sq.it is 727,4 people per km. The main feature of the Cattle Breeding Network of cattle breeding is that a large part of its products are produced in households. "The average size of the land plots belonging to them is 0,15 hectares. 94 percent of cattle accounts for the share of households. [2]

"The lack of the right to own land, the limitation of the granting of land to the subparagraph, makes it difficult for the formation of a redistribute market mexanizm between their owners and users. As a result, land users do not have the opportunity to manage land plots at their own discretion – that is, it is difficult to sell additional land for the purpose of expanding production. [3]

Land users who do not operate in this regard and are working inefficiently can not dispose of the excess land by transferring it to users who work actively or efficiently. In addition, the existing land use procedure does not provide for the possibility of using land as a guarantee in obtaining a loan, which seriously limits the financial capabilities of agricultural producers.

It is worth noting that while fermers do not fully believe that their right to land is inviolable, they will not invest in increasing labor productivity as well as improvingthe productivity of the land provided for the use of local government. It is important to balance the use of agricultural land as one of the factors affecting the efficiency of investment in the Cattle Breeding Network.

As is known, 70 per cent of the crop areas of Uzbekistan are used for cultivationof cotton. In the last few years, some land plots were removed from the cultivation of cotton and Willow. In our opinion, the additional fields used for planting these two products in the development of livestock should be used as a later date. Their area decreased by 40 percent due to the abundant and unsystematic feeding of livestock, the replacement of feedings was eliminated, and the quality of feedings was not restored. Part of the Emir Springs was transferred to the reserve land category, another part to the forest fund.

Cattle breeding is embodied mainly in peasant and farmer farms operating in irrigated areas, these farms are cultivated forage, creating a ground for the development of cattle breeding. Cattle breeding, in turn, contributes to the development of other

sectors of farms. This means that it is desirable that the economic networks will be developed interrelated. But, at present, this situation is deteriorating due to the complete non-compliance with the requirements of **scientific** and practical-based crop rotation. Indeed, the salinity of fodder crops in the composition of crop fields has been reduced to the standard. For example, "in 2010-2019 years, the salinity of fodder crops in crop fields was only 5.3 per cent. 3.7 percent of this corresponds to the contribution of perennial crops. [11], [12]

In most part of the agricultural enterprises of the Republic, the fact that the livestock feed base is not at the required level, they are not sufficiently specialized affects not only the decrease in the head numbers of cattle, but also their productivity, as a result-a decrease in the volume of products grown in the network.

As a result of these cases, the number of livestock products grown in the enterprises of processing agricultural products has been increasing year by year. The increase in the

cost of livestock products was influenced by other factors than those mentioned above. For example, the material and technical base of cattle breeding is weak in demand. This situation leads to an increase in the expenditure of manual labor. Feed produced in processing enterprises, the rapid increase in the prices of products, etc. [13] [14]

It should also be noted that the Cattle-Breeding Network performs a specific function, such as raising funds for peasant and farmer farms and increasing it. Due to the low rate of bank deposits in Uzbekistan and the lack of confidence in banks in the past periods, the population does not widely use services such as spending the accumulated funds on profitable bank deposits and securities. This is especially true of rural people who do not have wide access to financial infrastructure. Although peasant farms do not have the qualifications and skills in the field of cattle breeding, the purchase and maintenance of livestock for them is one of the methods of spending and breeding their own funds. The number of livestock is the main indicator of the scale of livestock. In other words, the larger the size of the livestock farm, the more productive it is on average. In connection with the fact that 80% of farmer farms in the Republic

specialize in grain and cotton production, 5.6 percent of cattle and 4.4 percent of cows are embodied in them. Such a situation can not meet the demand for organic fertilizers of grain and corn fields. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to this issue in the future.

Cattle imported from abroad for the purpose of the development of breeding in the Republic are presented without fertilization (abduction). For this purpose, funds are provided from the state budget. In order to develop livestock, there is also a trust in the construction of specialized livestock complexes. It is necessary to pay great attention to their further development in the future. In order to develop livestock, in recent years, additional lands have been allocated for the purpose of strengthening their nutrient base, increasing the amount of nutrients by planting additional fodder crops on these lands. In recent years, the number of infrastructure entities in livestock production has also been developing. For example, in 2019, zooveteranery Punks, which provide various services to livestock, as well as those who sell feed materials, operate. But their activities have not been effective enough. Because the services rendered are at a much higher level.

The measures implemented ensure an increase in the amount of livestock products. As a result of this, livestock networks are also making a certain amount of profit. But the current state of the development and efficiency of livestock production does not fully meet the demand. Because the population of the Republic has not yet been fully provided with quality livestock products at the required level. Therefore, it is desirable to develop livestock in the future and to give priority to its effectiveness. It is time to pay special attention to the step-by-step development of the material and technical base of livestock farms meeting modern requirements. Taking into account the achievements of Science and technology in livestock buildings and facilities, it is necessary to adapt them, to provide them with appropriate means, to introduce new techniques, advanced technologies in the production of quality products with good care of livestock animals. It is only in the network that production processes are improved and labor productivity is increased. Development of breeding business, creating

viable livestock breeds, ensuring that they are more quickly applied to production,

bunda breed, the opportunity to achieve the expected result, which is also not forgotten to use the option of purchasing viable cattle extension.

Conclusion and Recommendations.

1. In order to strengthen the feed base of livestock, it is necessary to develop fields forage cultivation extension, crop rotation. It is necessary to attach special importance to the water supply of the fields in which the Bunda forage crops are planted, to improve the melioration condition and to use organic and mineral fertilizers at the required level. To solve this issue, it is also necessary to establish the receipt of the required level of nutritious nutrients produced at the enterprises of the processing industry on the basis of ration of the nutrients formed in livestock on time. Taking into account the urgency of this issue, the government of the Republic has developed ways of economic assistance to farms. In particular, to allocate preferential credits for the development of food production, for this purpose they are exempted from customs duties and other measures are established if imported technical and technological resources from abroad.

2. It is necessary to pay special attention to the attraction of foreign investments in this process. Because at the moment this issue is being solved very quietly.

Along with the above, it is also desirable to provide state support for the increase in the contractual prices of livestock products, taking into account the level of inflation. Because these products are mainly purchased by state-owned enterprises.

3. The positive solution of all the issues mentioned directly depends on the relations, knowledge, experience and encouragement of the workers and employees working in the networks. Therefore, it is necessary to further develop the mechanisms and ways to solve these issues. It is desirable to give workers' wages on time, as well as to organize a Real way of rewarding them taking into account the amount and quality of the products they have grown.

As a result of the solution of the above issues, livestock sectors will develop and their efficiency will increase.

References

- [1] On additional measures for the state support of the livestock production

sector. Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Tashkent. 29.01.2020y.

[2] United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) 2020 materials.

[3] YU. Yusupov. Uzbekistan agro-industrial sector: main points, features, correction. CABAR. Asia. 2019.

[4] Abykaev, Nurtay Abykevich. Investment potential and optimization of its use in a market economy thesis and abstract on the higher attestation Commission of the Russian Federation 08.00.05, doctor of Economics. 1999.

[5] A.A. Abdug'aniyev, A.A. Abdug'aniyev. Economy in Agriculture. – T.: TDIU, 2010-283 pages.

[6] Journal of Agriculture and water resources of Uzbekistan. №11. 2020

[7] Prof. Dr AP faure. Investments: An Introduction. 2013-154 pages.

[8] P.I. Vaxrin, A.S. Neshitoy. Investment. Moscow. 2005 -381 pages.

[9] L.L. Igonina. Investment. Moscow, Economist. 2005- 478 pages.

[10] Stat.uz the. Has prepared a database of statistics of Republic of Uzbekistan.

[11] www.agro.uz. 2020 y

[12] I. Ergashev - Increasing innovation potential and investment activity in the development of Effective Entrepreneurship. Economic archive year LXXI, book 4-2018

[13] Pozilovich, K. J. (2020). Efficiency of innovative development of agricultural business in the Republic of Uzbekistan. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development, 5(ICIPPS), 4-4.

[14] Qurbonov, Ja. P., Sotvoldiyev, E.M. Formation of economic science., 52-54.